

Media Data Space

Digital European Platform of Quality Content Providers – Phase II

Workshop Synthesis Report

Day 2 collaborative workshop, 28th February 2022

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1. Context

This document summarises the most relevant outcomes emerged during the collaborative workshop held on 28th February 2022 in the context of the project “Digital European Platform of Quality Content Providers – Phase 2”. The project consists in a feasibility study for the creation of European data space in the media sector and is conducted on behalf of the European Commission – DG CNECT.

The objectives of the workshop included (i) clarifying the concept of data space in the European Media Sector; (ii) identifying possible use cases in the media sector; (iii) defining the key components of possible use cases and (iv) start building a coalition of media stakeholders who will co-design the best fit solution with the project team.

The workshop brought together around 30 different organizations from all around the European Media ecosystem. An overview is presented in the figure below.

Overall, the content of this document should be regarded as the initial step for the identification of relevant use cases to be used for the creation of a data space in the media sector.

2. Use cases – Preliminary List and prioritisation

2.1 Initial list of possible use cases

As a first step, a preliminary list of use cases was shared with the participants. The use cases were identified through a mix of desk research activities and interviews with relevant stakeholders in the media sector.

Before the workshop, participants were asked to assess through an online survey the proposed list of use cases according to two criteria, namely:

1. **Technological Feasibility**, i.e., the potential benefit that the development of a data space in the specific use case is expected to have in the media sector. Participants to the survey could assess the technological feasibility of the use case as:
 - High (*technology widely available within the market*)
 - Medium (*technology available but not widely adopted*)
 - Low (*cutting-edge technology – requirement for a preliminary assessment and testing*)

2. **Market Value**, i.e. a qualitative assessment of the impact that each specific use case could have on the media market. This is understood, for instance, as the potential to increase revenues, create new value chains or strengthen the current ecosystem in terms of content production and offer optimisation. The assessment was done according to a three-level scale:
 - High (*the impacts on the market can involve a wide range of media stakeholders*)
 - Medium (*the impacts on the market can involve specific groups of stakeholders or sub-sectors*)
 - Low (*small or unclear impacts on the market – to be further investigated*)

The table below provides the list of proposed use cases and the results of the pre-workshop survey, in terms of (average) perceived market value and technology feasibility for each use case:

ID	Use Case Title	Market value	Technological Feasibility
1	Adaptive Content Recommendations	High	High
2	Shared archiving: enhanced information retrieval	Medium	High
3	Optimized Streaming	Medium	Medium
4	Copyright & Anti-piracy	High	High
5	Audience Analysis	High	Medium
6	Translation of content	High	High
7	Fake-news detection	High	Medium
8	Addressable Advertising	High	Medium
9	Unified Access to non-live content	Medium	Medium
10	Enhanced Resource Management	Medium	Medium
11	Multi-site production	Medium	Medium
12	Media-live-on-the-go	Medium	Medium
13	Immersive Reality/Metaverse Content	Low	Low
14	Interactive Content - Gamification	Low	Low

From the analysis of the survey results, it emerged a number of use cases characterised by a combination of (perceived) high market value and relatively high technological feasibility and therefore identified by the study team as priority use case to be investigated.

The figure below visualises this relationship between average market value and technological feasibility indicated by the participants. Among the priority use cases in the top right quadrant, two were chosen to be discussed in depth during the collaboration workshop, namely:

- Adaptive content recommendations
- Copyright and anti-piracy

In addition, participants to the survey were also asked to suggest other potentially relevant use cases. The list below presents the main inputs received by respondents:

- Unified opt-in system for users within a blockchain
- Trusted digital news hub, Digital Right management
- Speech-to-text for regional markets

2.2 Main evidence collected from the discussion

During the workshop, the study team presented the outcomes of the survey to the attendees, who were subsequently invited to provide their comments and views. The following points summarise the main considerations made by the participants to the workshop, in relation to preliminary assessment of the use cases (in terms of technological feasibility and perceived market value):

- Some use cases can be aggregated or developed in parallel, since they present commonalities in terms of data types, business areas, and functionalities that the data space should have (e.g. production tools, services, users tailoring);
- It is important to distinguish the functionalities related to the whole Data Space, from those related to the specific use-case(s);
- When defining the roles of each stakeholder in the data space, it should be considered the whole value chain life-cycle of the data sharing (use case);
- The pandemic exacerbated issues and weaknesses of the European media ecosystem. This shed light on the importance that enhanced data sharing might have for companies which have to carefully allocate their budget and plan their strategies for recovery.

3. Detailed description of selected use cases

The two use cases discussed during the workshop were identified as a result of a mix research activities conducted at the initial stages of the project by the project team and the results of the survey conducted with the workshop participants.

Both use cases address two well-known problems emerged among media sector stakeholders, namely copyright protection (and related content remuneration) and the availability of data on users' content. The use case description is divided in two sections:

- i. an overall description of the use case, aiming at providing further details on the problems the use case is trying to solve, identify one or more proposed solutions and the benefits linked to the used case.
- ii. an outline of the governance model, which requested workshop participants to start sharing their opinions on possible relevant data types to be shared in each use case, discuss stakeholders' roles and a possible data governance model.

The following paragraphs provide a detailed description of both use cases, considering the evidence emerged during the workshop. The latter are also provided in the form of screenshots taken from the Mural dashboard used as online co-creation support tool during the workshop

3.1 Use case: Copyright protection and anti-piracy

3.1.1 Overall Description

Problem Solved

The preliminary problem identified by the Team stated: *“Media companies devote huge effort both in copyrights protection and content owners/producers remuneration. In parallel, they have to proactively fight piracy and unauthorised use of content that generate financial losses for the entire ecosystem”.*

The soft-infrastructure and the rules governing data sharing in a data space could provide an environment where tracking and usage policies over the shared data could be better enforced. Such data flow and content monitoring would apply to any type of content, from written and audio-visual including, theatrical, musical and artistic works.

The following image presents the evidence collected during the workshop:

From the discussion, the main aspect emerged was the need to improve copyright protection and ensure that remuneration goes to the correct right holders in a timely matter, which now represents a key issue. In addition,

some contents (e.g. news updates) include feeds and edits from many different sources, which makes tracking extremely difficult.

The following list summarises the main points emerged from the discussion, as also shown in the screenshot above:

- **Actors involved:** there is a huge range of stakeholders potentially involved, from international actors, to individual producers and end-users. This aspect, matched with the intermediate reworkings on contents (e.g. on news updates), makes it even more difficult to accurately track usage and identify copyright infringements. Also, some actors (especially platforms) are not willing to share usage data on the contents they provide/broadcast.
- **Standards:** the lack of common standards across countries is seen as a main obstacle to accurate rights remuneration and copyrights protection. It was highlighted that national differences in rules and standards exists also at the level of collecting societies.
- **New solutions and technologies:** focusing on technology, the participants agreed that specific technological enablers should be put in place to improve large-scale content tracking. In particular, tools able of automatically identifying contents (e.g. audio used in video) or allowing for effective tracking of contents across many platforms. Such tools would allow to secure Intellectual Property (IP) and improve remuneration through effective performance-based measuring.

Proposed Solution

According to the set of problems identified, the following step consists in identifying a number of solutions that could help solving those problems. The solutions in fact correspond to key functionalities that the data space should have to respond to the needs of media stakeholders in relation to the identified use case. The following image presents the evidences collected during the workshop:

- **Standards and interoperability**, in terms of both rules and procedures:
 - Cross-sector standardised data collection (on broadcast, consumptions, etc.)
 - Establishment and implementation of specific rules to ensure interoperability for each content type
 - Standardisation of usage reporting and harmonisation in the use of content identifiers
 - Adoption of Metadata unified identifiers for right holders and generalisation
 - Development of shared recommendations and incentives to adopt common standards
- **Enhanced data sharing**, mainly related to the sharing of usage data from different platforms.

- **Tools for improved identification**, all revolving around automation and simplification of operations based on common standards:
 - Adoption of tools for automatic identification of right holders, based on:
 - Interoperable identifiers and authorship tracking systems
 - Fingerprinting distributed solution or blockchain architectures (in relation to the latter, it was also raised the point that some solutions might be more costly/energy-consuming than others and this environmental aspect should be taken into consideration)
 - Dataspace-specific aspects, directly suggesting functionalities of the data spaces, were:
 - Development of specific connectors to improve data interoperability, possibly linked to watermarking tools
 - Make sure that usage data is included as primary type of data to be shared in the data space, to allow proper right holder participation (probably based on performance metrics)

Concrete Benefits

This use case would be able to improve media sector in many ways, including:

- Improving revenue schemes, i.e. helping the media ecosystem and facilitating the creation of new content;
- Creating trust among stakeholders through accurate and fair remuneration of right holders
- Economies of scale through the identification of standards that could be applied to any actor and to any new content type available
- Reducing the burdens related to content tracking and to the identification of right-holders and content mis-use (and consequent legal spill-overs)

Very much aligned to the above, the workshop further expanded the list potential concrete benefits related to the creation of a data space for this use case, as shown in the following image.

Overall, the topic of transparency raised generalised consensus. Other proposed benefits of the suggested solutions discussed during the workshop include:

- **Increased efficiency:**
 - Accuracy in right holder identification
 - Faster and increased revenues/remuneration
 - Overall improvement in operations

- Increased trust:
 - More efficient fight against piracy
 - Better knowledge of contents reuse and increased transparency
 - Better rights tracking and monitoring
- Favour quality and creation of new contents
 - Foster creativity and new content creation through ensured remuneration
 - Ease fair and compliant content repurposing

3.1.2 Governance Model

Data types

Before the workshop, relevant data types identified for this use case included (i) metadata and (ii) usage data, Other types of data identified as potentially relevant for this use case were content data.

The workshop has further detailed possible data formats relevant for this use case, as shown in the figure below:

A summary of the most relevant aspects emerged during the discussion on data types is presented below:

- **Metadata**, emerged as the main type of data relevant for this use case. Copyright tracking activities mainly rely on metadata for identifying right holders. These include:
 - Content IDs and standard identifiers for contents
 - Data composition identifiers, identifying parts of compound/complex contents shared
 - Rights holders' identifiers
- **Usage data**, both quantitative and qualitative such as:
 - Usage-related metrics on number of viewers or type of contents viewed
 - Audience insights and contextual information, (e.g. type of device, type of platforms, used to access contents)
- **Personal data**, providing information on end-users and consumers:
 - Data on subscriptions
 - More general information such as average prices paid for subscriptions also in relation to demographics (e.g. wage ranges, etc.)
- **Commercial data**, necessary for remuneration calculation and tailoring:
 - Price & financial data on services and content access
 - Detailed commercial data based on different usage contexts

- **Content data**, which could be relevant to timely identify mis-usage, especially for complex/reworked contents. Availability of content data would help in better monitoring content modifications along the value chain, avoiding improper usage and plagiarism. This aspect is mostly related to copyrights protection aspects, more than to anti-piracy, as pointed out by participants.

Stakeholders Involved and Roles

Before the workshop, many possible relevant stakeholder categories for this use case were identified. Out of that long-list, the team identified a number of priority stakeholders for this specific use-case, these being:

- Private and Public Broadcasters
- News media companies
- News publishers
- Advertisers
- Creative agencies
- Digitally native publishers
- Digital Audio and Radio Services
- Freelance journalists, content producers and online content producers

This preliminary list was used to start the discussion during the workshop. The discussion confirmed some of the identified categories and highlighted relevant others, as emerges from the figure below:

The participants to the workshop (mostly related to broadcasting and audio-visual content production) populated each of the main roles in the data space with the following stakeholders:

- **Data providers:**
 - Publishers and newsrooms
 - Distributors, platforms and
 - Independent producer
 - Content owners (providing metadata)
 - Social media and end-users
 - DRM and watermarking companies
 - IT and Telecommunication companies
 - Standard ID databases
- **Data users:**
 - Regulators
 - Media service providers
 - OTT providers
 - Collective management organisations
- **Intermediaries:**
 - Collective management organisations and copyright collectives

- Standards organisations and related authorities/institutions
- Other roles:
 - Individual authors, (empowered to share their data in the data space)
 - Policy makers
 - Trust services providers in the data space

Best-fit governance model

The workshop allowed to discuss different possible governance settings, the best possible data governance and management approach to be implemented in the use case.

In relation to each one of the three proposed types of governance models for this use case, the participants identified the following opportunities and challenges:

- Centralised model:
 - Opportunities (pros): seen as an efficient model. Questions arise on the selection process for the entity having responsibility on data quality (elected by participants?)
 - Challenges (cons): Market domination by large platforms and influence of lobbies; Trust by data owners in sharing; and mostly the huge number of potential participants that would make very difficult to find agreements or arrange a system based on individual authorisations
- Decentralised model:
 - Opportunities (pros): Seen as a fair model for both large and small organisations; Flexible and capable of ensuring trust. This would provide incentives for data owners to share their data, reaching the critical 'data mass' needed.
 - Challenges (cons): Mostly related to the adoption of common templates and recommendations. The development of a suitable legal framework and in particular agreeing on specific data sharing rules beforehand are seen as a major theme to ensure feasibility.
- Mediated Centralised model:
 - Opportunities (pros): Considered feasible on the basis of previous experiences and successful existing 'membership-style' governance models. It has the potential to increase trust in fair remuneration and confirm full sovereignty over the data shared, which is a crucial (but also challenging) aspect.
 - Challenges (cons): Some are common with the Centralised model, i.e. the need for an independent central entity; the importance of establishing clear workflows to increase data re-use; and the difficulty to find consensus and align a wide number of stakeholders.

3.2 Use case: Adaptive content Recommendations

3.2.1 Overall Description

Problem to be solved

The main issue addressed by this use case can be presented as follows: *research worldwide indicates that a large number of information published today finds no or very few users. In parallel, the media sector is experiencing high churn rates (due to the digital shift) and the growth of new phenomena, such as news fatigue and avoidance. In this context, it is increasingly important to create products and services responding to the actual needs and interests of consumers. However, nowadays media organisations have a limited availability of consumer data – revealing how readers interact with contents and useful to tailor the content offered – and no media organisation alone is capable to generate the amount of data needed to deploy cutting-edge analytical tools in the most effective way (e.g. artificial intelligence solutions, etc.).*

The main issue described above was further discussed during the workshop activities. A summary of the discussion is presented in the figure below.

During the workshop some of the key challenges linked to the main issue have been further investigated. The most relevant points of discussion are summarised below:

- **Lack of single data collection points:** the concept of tailored-made news needs a large number of data entry points which must be aligned both in terms of semantics and formats.
- **Legislative barriers** should also be further explored, focusing, for instance, on barriers associated to the collection and use of personal information
- **Fragmented environment and information systems**, where data is mainly held by technology giants, reduces the ability of media organisations to tailor their content to the users.

Additional elements emerged during the workshop, including:

- Further analysis should be conducted to better define the value generated by this use case for all the involved stakeholders. For example:
 - What is the value generated for users, as the types of data shared vary widely (i.e. articles, newsletters, subscriptions, shops products)?
 - How is value created through this use case? Drivers for data sharing have to be clear and explicit.
- The issue of identifying customer's preferences is a major obstacle for the implementation of a customer centric information, specifically in terms of:
 - Clustering of customer's preferences
 - Understanding the drivers of user's behaviour
 - Forms of content advised
 - Knowledge of the customer's lifetime value (CLV)

- Identifying a single user retention strategy is a complex task often unclear to business.
- Most companies in the media sector do not have the resources to manage increasing complexity and cope with the pace of new emerging technologies. In order to deal with an increasingly competitive market, there is the need for media outlets to share information and increase their analytical ability.

Proposed Solution

To address the above-presented problems, participants discussed together potential solutions. The proposed solution focuses on a number of core functionalities which will provide data (content data, metadata, usage date, personal/commercial data) to all actors, strengthening the ability of each organisation to provide content recommendations specific to the interests of every user.

An overview of the most relevant topics discussed is shared in the figure below.

The most relevant elements of the proposed solution discussed during the workshop can be summarised as follows:

- The proposed solution should consider a soft infrastructure able facilitate the exchange of all relevant data. This requires providing standards on (i) semantics; (ii) data formats; (iii) data analysis formats. In addition, guidelines to conduct audience analysis and address customer's preferences should be defined.
- The proposed solution should allow to segmentation of users according to their (i) browsing history (according to GDPR Regulations) and (ii) preferences and/or subscriptions that can be analysed through AI solution.
- The proposed solution should integrate data held by advertising companies

Concrete Benefits

A number of concrete benefits were also linked to the use case. The most important initially identified are:

- Improved ability of every organisation to understand customers' preferences and efficiently offer content in line with customer's preferences;
- Involvement of the whole supply-chain which to guarantee a wide range of data types and services in the data space;
- Traceability of the published data, i.e. guaranteeing to keep data ownership and copyrights protection;
- Use of a shared infrastructure allows to easily combine other services to the data space without further preliminary operations (e.g. translation);
- Data sovereignty is guaranteed by appropriate federation at the individual data level (specific usage policies);

The workshop allowed to further discuss on the potential benefits of a data space developed to address this use case. A summary of the discussion is presented in the figure below and further explained in the following paragraph.

Interesting benefits, emerged from the discussion, include:

- The use of common data management approaches, infrastructures and guidelines across organisations joining the media data space will reduce the complexity associated to the analysis of data related to customer’s preferences. This is expected to lead to a flattening of the learning curve and enable all the players in the market (including small organisations) to cope with emerging technologies (often perceived as a barrier).
- In parallel, the reduced complexity will also generate a reduction in the costs for each organisation for the data analysis.
- Finally, by having shared guidelines for analysis, organisations will be more efficient in identifying market changes by extrapolating concrete evidences from data, thus facilitating their capacity to respond in time with business actions.

3.2.2 Governance Model

Data types

Before the workshop, the following key data types were identified for this use case: (i) metadata (i.e. data describing content data); (ii) usage data; (iii) content data (based on the sub-sector of application). Other types of data identified as potentially relevant for this use case include (i) personal data and (ii) commercial data.

During the workshop activities, participants were asked to further detail the data types. The result is presented in the following diagram.

Related to content data, the following concrete examples have been provided:

- News content
- News classification
- Content from advertising industry
- List of entities who contribute and data providers
- Media Content

In terms of metadata, a series of more specific types of data have been identified, such as:

- IPTC topics
- TV Content metadata
- Advertising metadata
- Length, duration and story lifetime circle

Usage data that have been identified to populate the data entry points to support the content recommendations algorithms include:

- Scroll depth
- Click events

The personal data needed to cluster customer's preferences are:

- First party identifier
- End-user data

An element to be verified in terms of personal data is the normative alignment with respect to GDPR¹.

Commercial data mentioned include:

- User data from advertising industry
- Transaction data such as subscriptions

Based on the collected evidences, the post workshops activities will focus on expanding the possible concrete benefits with respect to the single data types identified and align them with the stakeholders to be involved.

Stakeholders Involved and Roles

Before the workshop, the project team mapped many possible relevant stakeholder categories that could be actively involved in a media data space. Out of that long-list, the team identified a number of priority stakeholders for this specific use-case, these being:

- Private and Public Broadcasters
- News media companies
- News publishers
- Advertisers
- Creative agencies
- Digitally native publishers
- Digital Audio and Radio Services
- Freelance journalists, content producers and online content producers

Based on the proposed sub-list of stakeholders, during the workshop the participants were asked to plot possible categories with respect to the different roles that they potentially could play in the future media data space. The results are shown in the diagram below:

¹ The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the Data Protection Law Enforcement Directive and other rules concerning the protection of personal data.
Source: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-topic/data-protection_en

What emerged from the workshop activity is that the identified data providers include:

- Media Content Producers such as:
 - Audio-visual companies
 - Advertising companies
 - News agencies
 - News publishers
 - Digital audio and radio services
- Potential users of the data published are:
 - Media entities such as:
 - Advertising companies
 - Broadcasters
 - News agencies
 - Content producers
 - Data agencies
- Intermediaries that facilitate the exchange of data include:
 - Tech companies
 - Data space providers
 - Social media entities

Best-fit governance model

During the workshop, stakeholders briefly discussed the governance model for this use case, including aspects of data privacy and sovereignty. In relation to privacy and data sovereignty several aspects were discussed by the participants:

As emerges from the screenshot above, the main elements mentioned during the discussion on **sovereignty and privacy** included:

- The importance of allowing each entity to define the exposition and usage perimeter at the individual data level;
- Another important element is the clarification of the rights and duties of each member of the governance model
- The data space must thus ensure flexible access rights so that the security and ownership of the dataset is ensured

A brief discussion on the possible **governance models** also took place, highlighting the following:

- From a technology perspective, a fully decentralised model would be the preferred one, where each entity holds operative control over the data published in the data space, according to agreed standards.
- A mediated centralised model resulted to be the most voted for this use case, where a specific entity defines the long-term strategy of the initiative, but each entity holds operative control over the data shared
- The previous point has to be read in the light of participants' concerns over the effective adoption of common standards, which is seen as a key aspect for a successful implementation of the data space. In this respect, it was suggested a centralised approach to the application of data sharing standards, as a preferred option to ensure interoperability and seamless data flows.